

IMPROVING OF THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF MG-ALLOY COMPOSITES PRODUCED BY POWDER METALLURGICAL TECHNIQUE

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SUMMARY: Metal matrix composites of QE22 magnesium alloy reinforced with SiC particles of different shapes were produced using powder metallurgical technique. Particle content of up to 25 volume per cent was chosen. The fracture toughness tests were carried out at room temperature and at 125°C in the as extruded as well as in the T6 heat treated condition. The reinforcement decreases in general the fracture toughness of the alloy QE22. Sharp irregular SiC particles reduce the fracture toughness of composites more than that of the blocky type. This was observed for composites tested under all experimental conditions.

KEYWORDS: fracture toughness, magnesium alloy, SiC particles, powder metallurgical technique

INTRODUCTION

Light metal matrix composites offer higher specific strength, higher elastic moduli, wider temperature range for application and lower thermal expansion than conventional light metals and alloys. These can be exploited by designers seeking high temperature strength, dimensional stability and light weight. Although aluminium and its alloys have been frequently used as the light metal for the matrix of MMCs, magnesium alloys with a much lower density have recently been considered as an alternative to Al for the matrix [1-3]. Incorporation of ceramic reinforcements into a light metals matrix enhances markedly the physical and mechanical properties of these metals, but the composites exhibit low fracture-related properties, which limit their widespread application [4-6]. Therefore, the fracture toughness behaviour of metal matrix composites has been the subject of the recent studies [7,8]. The examination of the effect of the particles shape and content on the fracture toughness of a magnesium alloy, QE22, which is a heat treatable and relatively temperature resistant magnesium alloy was the main objective of the present work.

TEST PROCEDURE

Powder metallurgical technique was used to produce metal matrix composites. For the matrix QE22 magnesium alloy powder of 39 µm average diameter was prepared by gas atomizing. The alloy powder was mixed with SiC particles of 9 µm average diameter. The consolidation of the cold prepressed alloy powder-particle mixture was carried out by extrusion. Two types of particle shapes, blocky and sharp, were used to examine the effect of the particle shape on the mechanical properties of composites. The content of SiC particles

reinforcement was in all cases 25 volume per cent. Unreinforced QE22 magnesium alloy powder was consolidated under the same conditions for use as a reference material to compare the mechanical properties. Examination of the unreinforced alloy and composites were carried out on samples in the as extruded as well as in the T6 condition. For the T6 heat treatment the specimens were solution treated at 530°C for 6 h followed by air cooling and ageing for 8h at 204°C. The microstructures of alloy and composites were examined by light microscopy. Fracture toughness tests were carried out at room and elevated temperature using the short rod specimen method of measuring fracture toughness [8-10]. The fracture surfaces of the tested specimens were examined in the scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The micrographs of the figures 1 and 2 show the microstructures of the materials tested. Figure 1 shows the particle distribution for composites of 20 volume per cent of blocky and sharp particles respectively. The SiC particles are aligned in the extrusion direction. The microstructure of the matrix alloy of the composite contains much finer precipitates than the unreinforced QE22, (Fig. 2a). A comparison of the microstructure of the composite in the extruded and in the T6 condition indicates that the particles facilitated the precipitation of the second phase, which may be $Mg_{12}Nd$ or $Mg_{12}Nd_2Ag$, (Fig. 2b) [11-14].

*Fig. 1: Microstructure of extruded QE22 + 20 vol. % SiC composites.
a) Blocky shape particles, b) Sharp shape particles.*

Fig. 2: Microstructure of QE22 + 20 vol. % SiC composites
a) as extruded, b) as T6 heat treated condition.

The fracture toughness tests of materials in extruded condition were carried out at room temperature and at 125°C, as well as in the T6 heat treated condition. Figure 3 shows the results of fracture toughness of unreinforced and composites reinforced by SiC particles of blocky type. The fracture toughness values of composites decrease with increasing content of the reinforcement independently of test conditions. However, the T6 heat treated composites reveal lower fracture toughness compared with those extruded. The results of fracture toughness values of specimens carried out at 125°C were higher than those tested at room temperature.

Fig. 3: Showing the results of fracture toughness tests on QE22 alloy and composites with blocky type SiC particles

Figure 4 shows the results of fracture toughness of composites reinforced by SiC particles of the sharp type. The fracture toughness values of composites were lower compared with the unreinforced alloy. The fracture toughness values of composites reinforced by the SiC particles of the sharp type show little change with increasing content of particles. These unexpected results may be due to proper distribution of the particles in the matrix alloy and the production procedure as a whole. The differences between the fracture toughness values of these composites in the as extruded as well as T6 condition were not as much observed as by

composites with SiC particles of blocky type. Nevertheless, composites with SiC Particles of the blocky type show higher fracture toughnesses over the whole particle content range than those of sharp type, (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Showing the results of fracture toughness tests on QE22 alloy and composites with sharp type SiC particles

Fig.5: The effect of particle shape on fracture toughness values of composites at RT.

The fractograph of the fracture surfaces of composites showed a preferentially oriented fracture plane in the extrusion direction (Fig. 6). In addition the fracture surface of composites revealed mainly a brittle fracture appearance. Occasionally some dimples like ductile fracture around the particles and frequently in the form of the elongated dimples in the extrusion direction on the plane perpendicular to the fracture surface were observed (Figs. 7, 8). The micrographs of figure 1 indicate on proper distribution of the reinforcement but sometimes clustering of the particles due to poor mixture of alloy powder and particles was observed (Fig. 8). This may be one reason for the scatter of the results.

Fig. 6: A fractograph of the short rod specimen of the composites with 20 vol. % SiC particles (blocky type)

Fig. 7: Showing the fracture surface of a composite tested with some elongated dimples

Fig. 8: Showing an example of SiC particles clustering and dimple like fracture around some particles

CONCLUSION

1. The QE22 magnesium alloy may be reinforced using powder metallurgical technique by SiC particles of blocky and sharp shapes.
2. As a result of production route the composites show directionally oriented microstructures in the extrusion direction.
3. The SiC particles are responsible for the fine microstructure in composites and facilitate the precipitation of the second phase on T6 heat treatment.
4. The fracture toughness of the QE22 alloy decreases with the SiC particle reinforcement. However, the decrease in fracture toughness depends on the particle shape and content. The fracture toughness of the composites as improved more in the case of blocky type particles as reinforcement than for the sharp particles.
5. T6 heat treatment of the composites causes additional embrittlement of the composites.
6. The particles facilitate crack formation on loading. This may be confirmed by the effect of particle shape on fracture toughness of tested composites.

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